

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RUDD (*SCARDINIUS ERYTHROPHthalmus*) DISTRIBUTED IN ULLISHORKUL LAKE, KHOREZM REGION

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Abstract

This article examines the morphometric characteristics of the *Scardinius erythrophthalmus* (rudd) population sampled from Ullisho'rko'l Lake in Khorezm Region. During the study, statistical evaluation was conducted on the main morphological traits (l, c, ao, o, hc, H, fin lengths and distances) of body and head proportions in 25 individuals. The results revealed overall stability of body proportions in the population, alongside moderate phenotypic variability in the head segment (hc/c) and certain fin characteristics. The average body length of 196.04 ± 2.97 mm and the coefficient of variation for most traits remaining within the 3–9 % range confirm the morphometric homogeneity of the population. Relatively higher variability in the head region is explained by differences in ecological conditions and age groups. The obtained data provide an important scientific basis for assessing the ecological adaptability, population structure, and biological status of this species in the water body.

Keywords: *Scardinius erythrophthalmus*, morphometrics, statistical analysis, population structure, Ullisho'rko'l Lake, ecological adaptability.

Introduction

Ullisho'rko'l Lake is the largest natural lake in the Khorezm Region of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is located 14 km southeast of the city of Khiva. The southern part of the lake extends into the territory of Turkmenistan. The total area of Ullisho'rko'l Lake is 14.8 km², its elevation is 86 m above sea level, its length from north to south is 16 km, and its width reaches 4 km. The lake is mainly fed by collector-drainage waters and excess irrigation water flowing from fields in its northern part (National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2005).

Scardinius erythrophthalmus (Linnaeus, 1758) is a freshwater fish species widely distributed in Europe and Central Asia. Although this species has limited direct commercial value, it plays an important role as a food source for predatory fish inhabiting freshwater ecosystems (Özgür Emiroğlu, 2010).

The species is typically found in slow-flowing rivers, lakes, and reservoirs, showing good adaptation to environments rich in aquatic vegetation. The rudd exhibits feeding habits that can vary depending on temperature and season. In general, its diet includes various aquatic plants along with small animal organisms and detritus (Nurminen et al., 2003). The feeding intensity of rudd is positively correlated with water temperature (Kapusinski et al., 2012).

Morphometric parameters of *Scardinius erythrophthalmus* specimens collected from the Shumarovka River and Chistoye Lake in Russia have been studied, and their morphometric characteristics were compared (A.S. Mavrin et al., 2017). In the freshwater river systems of Arkhangelsk Province, Russia, coefficients of variation were examined for the overall populations of *Scardinius erythrophthalmus* aged 1+ to 4+.

The results revealed considerable variability in growth-related traits such as maximum and minimum body height, total length, and standard length of the fish (M. Klymenko et al., 2022).

Analysis of morphometric characteristics of fish remains one of the most reliable research methods in ichthyology, a technique that has been applied for many years and still retains its relevance today.

Continuation of the translation:

Studying the morphometric characteristics of *Scardinius erythrophthalmus* makes it possible to determine the population structure, biological features, and ecological adaptability of this species. Its body structure, fins, and relative dimensions of the head may exhibit variability depending on environmental conditions. Moreover, these data have important scientific and practical significance for fisheries management, rational use of natural resources, and the conservation of biodiversity.

The purpose of our research is to determine the morphometric indices of *Scardinius erythrophthalmus* relative to body and head length and to highlight their biological and ecological importance.

Materials and Methods

Research on *Scardinius erythrophthalmus* was conducted in August 2025 in Ullisho'rko'l Lake, Khorezm Region. The species composition of the caught fish was identified using the guides of Berg (1948) and Mirabdullayev (2011). Collection of material in the study area was carried out according to generally accepted ichthyological methods (Pravdin, 1966). As a result of the research, 25 specimens of rudd (*Scardinius erythrophthalmus*) were collected from the lake. The length and weight of the fish were measured,

and morphometric characteristics were determined (Pravdin, 1966).

In the statistical analysis of morphometric traits, the following parameters were calculated: range (Lim),

mean (M) and its error (m), standard deviation (σ), variance, coefficient of variation (Cv %), and differences between traits (Lakin, 1990).

The exact locations where fish samples were caught in the study area were recorded, and geographic coordinates were determined (Table 1).

Table 1

Coordinates of the catching locations of *Scardinius erythrophthalmus*

Sampled area	Coordinate points	Width (°)	Length (°)
Lake Ullishorkul	41°15'45.95"N 60°28'54.63"E	41.26276	60.48184
	41°15'44.03"N 60°29'05.06"E	41.26223	60.48474
	41°15'39.54"N 60°28'43.46"E	41.26098	60.47874
	41°15'25.54"N 60°28'58.7"E	41.25709	60.48297
	41°15'18.98"N 60°29'12.1"E	41.25527	60.48669

Figure 1. General view of Ullisho'rko'l Lake located in Khorezm Region (Republic of Uzbekistan) and the points where fish samples were collected.

Continuation of the translation:

The coordinates obtained from Ullisho'rko'l Lake confirm that rudd is distributed throughout the entire lake and demonstrate the ecological diversity of the population. These data increase the reliability of the morphometric analysis results and provide a scientific basis for studying the spatial structure of the population. The material collected on the basis of these coordinates was analyzed, and the morphometric characteristics of the fish caught in the area were determined.

Results and Discussion

The morphometric characteristics of the studied fish were statistically analyzed.

Relative to body length (standard length, l):

The average body length (l) was 196.04 ± 2.97 mm, with a coefficient of variation (Cv) of 7.58%. This indicates moderate variation in body length within the population.

Snout length (Ao) ($4.68 \pm 0.07\%$) and eye diameter (O) ($4.27 \pm 0.04\%$) showed small values, with relatively low variation (Cv = 4.90–7.93%).

For the majority of traits, the coefficient of variation ranged between 3–9%, which indicates stability of morphometric characteristics in the population (Table 2).

Relative to head length (c):

Head length (hc/c) showed the highest value at $16.30 \pm 0.32\%$, with a coefficient of variation of 9.75%, indicating noticeable differences in head shape.

Eye diameter (o/c) was $5.20 \pm 0.05\%$, snout length (ao/c) was $5.70 \pm 0.09\%$, and the coefficients of variation for these traits were around 5–7%. This shows that eye and snout dimensions are relatively stable (Table 2).

Table 2

Morphometric characteristics of rudd (<i>Scardinius erythrophthalmus</i>) from Ullisho'rko'l lake (n=25)					
Indicators	Lim.	M±m	Σ	S ²	Cv %
<i>l, mm</i>	168,00-222,00	196,04±2,97	14,85	220,54	7,58
As a percentage of body length (<i>l</i>)					
<i>c</i>	20,41–23,60	21,79 ± 0,16	0,78	0,62	3,60
<i>ao</i>	4,73–6,59	5,70 ± 0,09	0,43	0,18	7,49
<i>o</i>	4,73–5,67	5,20 ± 0,05	0,26	0,07	5,04
<i>po</i>	10,19–12,42	10,89 ± 0,11	0,53	0,28	4,89
<i>hc</i>	10,18–19,11	16,30 ± 0,32	1,59	2,53	9,75
<i>io</i>	7,64–9,22	8,39 ± 0,09	0,44	0,19	5,20
<i>H</i>	28,68–35,23	31,89 ± 0,30	1,51	2,28	4,73
<i>h</i>	9,44–11,36	10,44 ± 0,10	0,51	0,26	4,86
<i>aD</i>	49,09–56,25	52,73 ± 0,27	1,37	1,87	2,59
<i>pD</i>	30,99–38,25	34,41 ± 0,30	1,49	2,21	4,32
<i>Pl</i>	12,10–16,27	14,37 ± 0,20	1,02	1,04	7,10
<i>lD</i>	14,19–18,31	15,55 ± 0,17	0,85	0,72	5,45
<i>hD</i>	16,99–23,94	19,87 ± 0,35	1,77	3,12	8,89
<i>lA</i>	10,53–13,50	12,29 ± 0,17	0,87	0,76	7,08
<i>hA</i>	11,46–14,77	12,74 ± 0,17	0,85	0,72	6,68
<i>lP</i>	13,07–17,20	15,41 ± 0,21	1,06	1,13	6,91
<i>lV</i>	13,07–17,20	15,51 ± 0,20	0,99	0,97	6,36
<i>P–V</i>	23,33–26,53	24,65 ± 0,17	0,84	0,70	3,39
<i>V–A</i>	23,35–25,85	24,46 ± 0,14	0,71	0,51	2,91
As a percentage of head length (<i>c</i>)					
<i>ao/c</i>	22,58–29,73	26,14 ± 0,31	1,54	2,39	5,91
<i>o/c</i>	21,62–26,67	23,88 ± 0,27	1,35	1,83	5,67
<i>po/c</i>	48,39–52,63	49,98 ± 0,24	1,22	1,49	2,45
<i>hc/c</i>	45,95–85,71	74,86 ± 1,44	7,20	51,83	9,62
<i>io/c</i>	35,00–42,11	38,52 ± 0,41	2,03	4,11	5,27

Continuation and completion of the translation:

The obtained morphometric indices show that body proportions in the population are generally stable, while certain traits exhibit noticeable phenotypic variability. Traits such as maximum body depth (*H*) and minimum body depth (*h*) stand out with relatively high values, indicating that the species is well adapted to active movement in the upper water layers, rapid changes in direction, and stable swimming. The variation in fin-related indices (*ID*, *hD*, *lA*, *hA*) is moderate, meaning that the fins form a relatively uniform morphological complex within the population.

The relatively small proportions of snout length (*ao*), eye diameter (*o*), and interorbital distance (*io*) relative to body length reflect the species' adaptation to feeding on natural food objects—soft aquatic vegetation, detritus, phytoplankton, and small zooplankton organisms. The low coefficients of variation for these traits indicate that feeding-related adaptations are consistently formed in the population.

Among the indices calculated relative to head length, the greatest variability is observed in head depth (*hc/c*) ($Cv \approx 9.6\%$), suggesting that head morphology is significantly influenced by external factors, age stages, or individual nutritional condition. Such plasticity in the head segment is evidence of the population's high adaptability to local ecological conditions.

The final analysis shows that although the basic skeletal-muscular complex of the body structure is sta-

ble in the population, phenotypic variation in head proportions remains quite pronounced. This morphometric structure confirms the species' ecological plasticity and its ability to optimally maintain efficiency of movement and feeding under the conditions of the given water body.

Conclusion

The *Scardinius erythrophthalmus* population from Ullisho'rko'l Lake exhibits moderate variation in morphometric characteristics. The average body length is 196.04 ± 2.97 mm, and the stability of body proportions ($Cv = 3-9\%$) indicates relative morphological homogeneity of the population. At the same time, the higher variation observed in head depth ($Cv = 9.75\%$) is evidence of existing morphological diversity within the population. The elongated body shape and well-developed fins of the fish are important adaptive traits that ensure their ability to move effectively in water and maintain balance.

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